

On Colloidal Electrolytes. An Attempt to Account for the Variation of pH and Alkali Metal Ion Activity during the Titration of Clay Acids by Alkalis and to Find the Dissociation Constants of the Acids

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On the basis of the theory proposed by the author in previous publications, equations³ have been deduced connecting the pH with the ratio of the unneutralised to the neutralised portion of the clay acid and a quantity (θK_s) where K_s has been termed the surface dissociation constant and $\theta = C/(K_s + C)$ where C is the concentration (unit arbitrary) of the clay acid and K_s , a constant. The equation has been found to agree well with the experimental data of Marshall and Bergman on the titration of some clay acids. Another equation has also been deduced on the basis of the same theory connecting the alkali metal ion activity $(M)_c$ with the number of moles of alkali $(M)_t$ added to the acid suspension at constant volume and a quantity $(K\theta/Sxd)$, where θ has the same significance as stated already, K , a proportionality constant, x , the number of clay particles S , the surface area of each particle and d , the effective thickness of the diffuse double layer. The equation has been found to agree with the data of Marshall and Bergman.

THE researches of a large number of authors of whom only a few¹⁻³ are mentioned here have contributed to the present state of our knowledge of the electrochemical properties of the clay acids. In this paper an explanation for the variation of hydrogen and alkali metal ion activities with the degree of neutralisation of some clay acids by alkalis will be attempted on the basis of the theory which has been discussed in several recent publications⁹⁻¹¹. The assumptions which have a direct bearing on the subject matter of this paper are stated below :

(1) Each micelle or colloidal particle is surrounded by an electrical double layer made up of two parts, (a) the fixed Stern¹².Mukherjee¹³ layer and (b) the diffuse (i.e., Gouy-Chapman) layer.

(2) The counter ions cannot go beyond the boundary of the diffuse double layer of the particle to which they belong. When a particle moves sufficiently close to a reversible electrode placed in the sol so that the diffuse double layer is in contact with it, then only the counter ions present in that part of the double layer can register their activity on the electrode.

(3) Starting from the outermost boundary of the diffuse double layer, the number of the counter ions per unit volume increases according to the Boltzmann distribution law as the surface of the particle is approached.

The equation connecting pH with the degree of ionisation and the dissociation constant.

For the sake of simplicity, let us assume that all the particles of the clay acid are of the same size and

C is their concentration, expressed in an arbitrary unit, at which a fraction θ per unit of the surface of the reversible electrode is in contact with the diffuse double layers of the particles. Then the rate at which the bare portion $(1-\theta)$ per unit area of the surface of the electrode comes in contact with the double layers of fresh particles is $K_1(1-\theta)C$ and the rate at which they are removed from the surface is $K_2\theta$, where K_1 and K_2 are constants, provided the viscosity and temperature remain constant. At equilibrium we may write

$$K_1(1-\theta)C \doteq K_2\theta \quad \dots (1)$$

or

$$\theta = \frac{C}{K_0 + C}, \text{ where } K_0 = K_2/K_1$$

If the reversible electrode indicates $(H)_c$ as the hydrogen ion activity of the clay acid sol and $(H)_t$ be the hydrogen ion activity of the intermicellar liquid then

$$(H)_c = \theta(H)_s + (H)_t(1-\theta) \quad \dots (2)$$

where $(H)_s$ is a proportionally constant and may be interpreted to represent the activity of the hydrogen ions associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layer at the plane of constant with the electrode. From equation (2) it follows that :

$$(H)_c - (H)_t = [(H)_s - (H)_t]\theta \quad \dots (5)$$

For a well dialysed sol $(H)_t$ is very small and during titration it is the first to be neutralised and hence it

may be neglected compared to $(H)_s$ and $(H)_c$. Under this condition, therefore, equation (3) may be written as follows⁺ :

$$(H)_c = \theta(H)_s \quad \dots (4)$$

Let us now assume that $(H)_s$ is proportional (if not equal) to $(H)_a^n$ where $(H)_a$ is the effective H^+ ion activity within the diffuse double layer so that for the exchange of H^+ ions between the fixed Stern-Mukherjee layer and the diffuse double layer the following relation holds good :

$$(H)_a(\alpha) = K_a(1-\alpha) \quad \dots (5)$$

where K_a is the dissociation constant, (α) the degree of ionisation i.e., the bare fraction of the surface (Stern-Mukherjee layer) and $(1-\alpha)$ the fraction of the surface covered by the adsorbed H ions. Equation (5) may then be written as :

$$(H)_a = K_a(1-\alpha)/(\alpha) \quad \dots (6)$$

Putting $K'(H)_a^n$ for $(H)_s$ in equation (4) it follows from the equations (4) and (6) that

$$(H)_c = \theta K'(K_a)^n(1-\alpha)^n/(\alpha)^n = K_s\theta(1-\alpha)^n/(\alpha)^n \quad \dots (7)$$

where $K'(K_a)^n = K_s$ which may be termed the surface dissociation constant of the clay acid

Equation (7) may also be written as follows :

$$P(H)_c = P(\theta K_s) - n \log \left(\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha} \right) \quad \dots (8)$$

Considering the large amount of work done on polyacids a brief reference to some of them may be made here. Katchalsky and Spitnik¹⁴ and Arnold and Overbeek¹⁵ have noticed, that during the potentiometric titration of polyacrylic acids in the presence of a neutral salt, the variation of pH depends much on the concentration of salt. It has, therefore, been assumed by many authors that the dissociation constants of these acids are affected by the electric charge of the macromolecule. Overbeek¹⁶ has suggested that if K_0 be the dissociation constant of a COOH group, then the observed dissociation constant,

$$K = K_0 \exp. (-\Delta F/kT) \quad \dots (a)$$

where ΔF represents the extra amount of free energy per COOH group required to cause further dissociation when the molecule has already acquired a certain charge say Z_e . Combining equation (a) with the Henderson equation, the following equation has been obtained

$$P - PK_0 - \log \alpha/(1-\alpha) = \frac{0.434}{kT} \frac{\partial F}{\partial Z} = \frac{0.434}{kT} \Delta F \quad \dots (b)$$

⁺The H^+ ion activity of pure water is $10^{-7}N$. Therefore, when $(H) = 10^{-6}$ neglect of $(H)_i$ may involve an error of 10% or more according to conditions.

Using random coil as a model, Hermans and Overbeek¹⁷ and others^{18,19} have deduced, for different forms of charge distribution, expressions for the electrical free energy F and hence for ΔF , on the basis of the Debye-Huckel theory. It follows from equation (b) that ΔF can also be determined for different values of α by potentiometric titration when K_0 is known. The theoretical expressions for ΔF combined with the possibility of its determination for different values of α have provided incentive for further research on this line. A detailed investigation by potentiometric titration of polyglutamic acids^{20,21} and hydrolysed copolymers of maleic anhydride and alkyl vinyl ethers²² has been carried out with a view to obtain information on helix-coil transition in them and the energy change involved in such transition.

It may be mentioned that the ideal behaviour predicted from theory does not often agree with the experimental results, besides none of the aforesaid authors¹⁴⁻²² have taken the "sol concentration effect" into consideration. The question of helix-coil transition does not arise in the case of clay particles.

Verification of the Equations.

Marshall and Bergman^{23,24} have determined, by the potentiometric method, the activity of the H^+ , K^+ and NH_4^+ ions during the titration of four freshly electrolysed clay acids. Of these four clays, two of the montmorillonite type, bentonite (particle size; 0.2μ) from Wyoming and Putnum clay (particle size; 0.2μ) which consists mainly of beidelite, show considerable base exchange capacity and have, therefore, been selected for our purpose. The data on the neutralisation of these two clay acids will be considered up to the pH range corresponding to about 70% neutralisation as beyond this range the clay particles may disintegrate and hydrolysis may be appreciable.

In Table 1 are recorded the data, taken from Table 2 of Marshall and Bergman's²³ paper, corresponding to 26.3% neutralisation of Putnum clay.

TABLE 1—PUTNUM CLAY SUSPENSION (PARTICLE SIZE; 0.2μ)

Clay per cent C	θ	Moles KOH added per litre	percentage neutralisation	Values of pH	
				observed	calculated from eqn (4)
11.420	0.236	0.03	26.3	4.58	4.61
4.567	0.110	0.012	26.3	4.98	4.95
1.142	0.0299	0.003	26.3	5.51	5.51

In the Tables 2, 4 and 5 under the heading A.R. are recorded the number of moles of alkali required to neutralise one litre of the clay suspension

The constant in the Tables 1-5 have been found in the following way. $(1/H)$ has been plotted against $1/C$ (vide equation (4), the intercept of the

TABLE 2—PUTNUM CLAY SUSPENSION (PARTICLE SIZE : 0.2 μ)

Clay per cent C		θ	A.R.	Moles KOH added per litre	$\log(1-\alpha)/(\alpha)$	(θK_s)	Values of pH	
							observed	calculated from eqn(4)
11.42	0.236	0.114	0.01	1.023	5.05	5.05	3.75	3.88
11.42	0.236	0.114	0.02	0.672	5.05	5.05	4.27	4.29
"	"	"	0.03	0.447	"	"	4.58	4.55
"	"	"	0.04	0.267	"	"	4.78	4.75
"	"	"	0.05	+0.107	"	"	4.93	4.93
"	"	"	0.06	-0.046	"	"	5.03	5.10
"	"	"	0.07	-0.201	"	"	5.23	5.27
"	"	"	0.08	-0.372	"	"	5.90	5.47
1.142	0.0299	0.0114	0.003	+0.446	6.02	6.02	5.51	5.52
"	"	"	0.006	-0.046	"	"	6.08	6.07

straight line is $1/(H)_s$ and the slope is $K_0/(H)_s$. Again when pH is plotted against $\log(1-\alpha)/(\alpha)$ the intercept is $P(\theta K_s)$ and the slope is 'n'.

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that the values of pH corresponding to those of $(H)_c$ calculated from equation (4) taking $(H)_s = 1.03 \times 10^{-4}$ and K_0 (in θ) = 37 agree well with those observed by Marshall and Bergman²³. In Table 2 the same value of K_0 has been used to calculate θ . From the data recorded in Table 2 it will appear, that the agreement between the values of pH observed and those calculated from equation (8) is satisfactory in all the cases except two where the moles of KOH added per litre are 0.01 and 0.08. From the values of $P(\theta K_s)$ for the 11.42% and 1.142% suspensions of Putnum clay recorded in Table 2, the values of θK_s have been found and from these knowing θ in each case, the values of K_s have been calculated and recorded in Table 3. The average of these values

 TABLE 3—PUTNUM CLAY SUSPENSION (PARTICLE SIZE ; 0.2 μ)

Clay per cent C		θ	$P(\theta)$	$P(\theta K_s)$	$P(K_s)$	K_s
11.42	0.236	0.63	5.05	4.42	3.8×10^{-5}	
1.142	0.0299	1.52	6.02	4.50	3.2×10^{-5}	

of K_s viz., 3.5×10^{-5} may be taken as constant within the limits of experimental error. It may,

therefore, be concluded that the surface dissociation constant K_s of the sample of Putnum clay used remains constant when its concentration in the suspensions varies from 11.42% to 1.142% and the degree of ionisation varies between 20 and 60%. Mitra²⁵ has noticed that the dissociation constant of clay acid varies with its concentration. Obviously the quantity he has measured is θK_s in which θ varies with the concentration of the clay acid.

The data for the bentonite suspensions, recorded in Table 4, show that the linear relation between pH and $\log(1-\alpha)/(\alpha)$ holds good within the pH range 3.28 to 5.4. The slope n is 2.27 and is thus double of that (i.e., 1.13) found for Putnum clay. The concentration of the bentonite suspensions has been varied from 3.277 to 1.13% and within this narrow range, the value of K_0 (in θ) could not be found accurately. Assuming that its value is of the same order as in the case of Putnum clay, $\theta K_s/C$ may be taken as proportional to K_s and these have been recorded in column 5 of Table 5. Their average may be taken as proportional to K_s .

Marshall and Bergman have pointed out that the clay acids are unstable systems. Hence the pH and base exchange capacity (b.e.c.) of clay acid suspensions may change on standing. To get comparable results, it is necessary to estimate the b.e.c. before and after each set of experiments with reference to a

 TABLE 4—BENTONITE SUSPENSION PARTICLE SIZE ; (0.2 μ)

 n in eqn. (8) = 2.27

Clay per cent C	A.R.	Moles KOH added per litre	$\log(1-\alpha)/(\alpha)$	$P(\theta K_s)$	Values of pH	
					observed	calculated from eqn.(8)
3.277	0.0328	0.008	0.452	4.31	3.28	3.27
"	"	0.010	0.340	"	3.55	3.54
"	"	0.015	+0.072	"	4.11	4.15
"	"	0.020	-0.196	"	4.79	4.76
"	"	0.025	-0.506	"	5.40	5.46
2.00	0.0194	0.008	0.154	4.65	4.29	4.30
"	"	0.010	-0.027	"	4.68	4.71
"	"	0.012	-0.208	"	5.15	5.12
"	"	0.016	-0.627	"	5.74	6.17

TABLE 5

Clay per cent C	A.R.	$P(\theta K_s)$	(θK_s)	$\theta K_s/C$
3.277	0.0328	4.31	4.90×10^{-5}	1.49×10^{-5}
2.00	0.0194	4.65	2.24×10^{-5}	1.12×10^{-5}
		Average		1.31×10^{-5}

definite pH preferably below 8.0 as from pH 7.0 and above water acts as a weak acid.

Equation connecting the activity of the alkali metal ion with the amount of alkali added during titration.

Let $(M)_c$ represent the activity of the alkali metal ion measured by the potentiometric method when to a clay acid suspension of concentration C , $(M)_t$ moles of alkali have been added. If $(H)_c$ is high, the entire amount of alkali added will enter the diffuse double layers, the (OH) ions will combine with the H^+ ions there and the M^+ ions will take the place of the H^+ ions thus removed. The equilibrium between the adsorbed H^+ ions in the Stern-Mukherjee layer and those in the diffuse double layer will be disturbed and to restore equilibrium a few H^+ ions from the former shall pass into the latter. Assuming as negligible the activity of the alkali metal ions in the intermicellar liquid so long as the pH is low, we may write as in the case of the H^+ ions discussed already the following equation :

$$(M)_c = \theta(M)_s \quad \dots (9)$$

where θ has the same significance as explained already and $(M)_s$ is a proportionality constant representing the activity of the alkali metal ions associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact with the electrode.

Let x represent the number of clay particles present in the system, S , the surface area of each, d , the effective thickness of the diffuse double layer and $(M)_t$ the moles of alkali added. Then the concentration of the alkali metal ions in the diffuse double layer is $(M)_t/Sxd$, neglecting the few alkali metal

ions adsorbed in the Stern-Mukherjee layer. It is now assumed that $(M)_s = K(M)_t/Sxd$ where K is a constant. Substituting this value of $(M)_s$ in equation (9) we may write :

$$(M)_c = \theta K(M)_t/Sxd \quad \dots (10)$$

or $-\log(M)_c = -\log(M)_t - \log(\theta K/Sxd) \quad \dots (11)$

i.e., $P^{(M)}_c = P^{(M)}_t + P^{(\theta K/Sxd)} \quad \dots (11a)$

when the concentration of the clay acid in a suspension remains constant during titration $(\theta K/Sxd)$ also remains constant.

Verification of the equations.

The data published by Marshall and Bergman^{23, 24} have been utilised to test the aforesaid equations. During the titration of the clay acids by alkalis, these authors have measured the pH by using glass electrode and the alkali metal ion activity by using clay membrane electrodes. Their data are recorded in the Tables 6-9.

They have found that when the pH is low, (pH < 4) the H^+ ions interfere in the determination of the activity of the alkali metal ions and so corrections have to be introduced. We have introduced corrections taking the mobility ratio of H^+ to K^+ or NH_4^+ as 4.0. The corrected activity of the alkali metal ions has been recorded in column 5 of the Tables 6-9. It may be pointed out that the activity of the H^+ ions at the plane of contact of the diffuse double layers of the clay particles with the surface of the membrane electrode is quite high [viz., $(H)_s$] and hence arises the importance of the correction in the initial stages of addition of alkali during titration.

It will be noticed from the data recorded in the Tables 6 to 9 that the values of $P^{(M)}_c$ and $P^{(M)}_t$ are relatively large compared to their difference which is $P^{(\theta K/Sxd)}$. A small error in the determination of either $P^{(M)}_c$ or $P^{(M)}_t$ or both will, therefore, be magnified in the corresponding value of $P^{(\theta K/Sxd)}$. Furthermore, error in the determination of pH at the initial stage of titration will affect the correction of activity of the alkali metal ions necessitated

TABLE 6—pH AND POTASSIUM ION ACTIVITY DATA FOR PUTNUM CLAY SUSPENSIONS

Clay per cent C	pH	Moles KOH added per litre- $(M)_t$	Observed K^+ activity,	Corrected K^+ activity, $(M)_c$	$-\log(M)_c$	$-\log(M)_t$	$-\log(\theta K/Sxd)$
11.42	3.75	0.01	0.00180	0.00127	2.896	2.000	0.90
"	4.27	0.02	0.00244	0.00229	2.633	1.699	0.93
"	4.58	0.03	0.00343	0.00335	2.475	1.523	0.95
"	4.78	0.04	0.00462	0.00457	2.340	1.398	0.94
"	4.93	0.05	0.00626	0.00623	2.205	1.301	0.90
"	5.03	0.06	0.00753	0.00753	2.123	1.222	0.90
"	5.23	0.07	0.00870	0.00870	2.060	1.155	0.90
						Average	0.92
4.567	4.98	0.012	0.00157	0.00154	2.813	1.921	0.89
"	5.60	0.024	0.00252	0.00252	2.599	1.620	0.98
						Average	0.98

TABLE 7—pH AND POTASSIUM ION ACTIVITY DATA FOR BENTONITE SUSPENSIONS

Clay per cent C	pH	Moles KOH added per litre-(M) _t	Observed K ⁺ activity,	Corrected K ⁺ activity, (M)	-log(M) _c	-log(M) _t	-log (θK/S _{zd})
3.277	3.55	0.010	0.00375	0.00290	2.538	2.000	0.54
"	4.11	0.015	0.00443	0.00420	2.377	1.824	0.55
"	4.79	0.020	0.00591	0.00586	2.232	1.699	0.53
"	5.40	0.025	0.00678	0.00678	2.169	1.602	0.57
						Average	0.55
1.31	4.44	0.004	0.00092	0.00080	3.097	2.398	0.70
"	5.26	0.006	0.00122	0.00120	2.921	2.222	0.70
"	5.81	0.008	0.00146	0.00146	2.836	2.097	0.74
						Average	0.71

TABLE 8—AMMONIUM ION ACTIVITIES IN PUTNUM CLAY SUSPENSION

Clay per cent C	pH	Moles NH ₄ OH added per litre-(M) _t	Observed NH ₄ ⁺ activity,	Corrected NH ₄ ⁺ activity, (M) _c	-log(M) _c	-log(M) _t	-log (θK/S _{zd})
9.00	4.81	0.008	0.00048	0.00044	3.36	2.10	1.26
"	5.26	0.020	0.00108	0.00108	2.97	1.70	1.27
"	5.47	0.032	0.00184	0.00184	2.74	1.50	1.24
						Average	1.26

TABLE 9—AMMONIUM ION ACTIVITIES IN BENTONITE SUSPENSION

Clay per cent C	pH	Moles NH ₄ OH added per litre-(M) _t	Observed NH ₄ ⁺ activity,	Corrected NH ₄ ⁺ activity, (M) _c	-log(M) _c	-log(M) _t	-log (θK/S _{zd})
3.00	3.57	0.0090	0.0030	0.00218	2.662	2.046	0.62
"	4.10	0.0135	0.00366	0.00342	2.468	1.870	0.60
"	4.80	0.0180	0.00447	0.00442	2.355	1.745	0.61
"	5.23	0.0225	0.00566	0.00566	2.247	1.648	0.60
"	5.83	0.0270	0.00631	0.00631	2.200	1.569	0.63
						Average	0.61
0.50	4.17	0.001	0.000372	0.00017	3.770	3.000	0.77
"	5.00	0.002	0.000431	0.00040	3.397	2.699	0.70
"	5.98	0.003	0.000541	0.00054	3.268	2.523	0.75
						Average	0.74

by the interference of the H⁺ ions. Taking all these sources of error into account, the constancy of the value of $P^{(\theta K/S_{zd})}$ for a given concentration of a clay suspension may be considered satisfactory. Attention may also be drawn to the fact that when the concentration of clay in a suspension is diminished by dilution, both θ and x diminish but $\bar{d}$ tends to increase. Therefore, when a clay acid suspension is diluted, change in θ may preponderate over that of the product of x and $\bar{d}$ and hence $P^{(\theta K/S_{zd})}$ may increase with dilution. The data recorded in the aforesaid tables support this conclusion.

It may also be pointed out that as the pH increases during titration, the activity of the alkali metal ion say (M)_t in the intermicellar liquid also increases and above a certain pH it can no longer be neglected compared to (M)_c. Hence deviation from the simple equation (9) is expected above a certain pH. A

more general equation which should be of the same form as equation (2) may be written as follows :

$$(M)_c = \theta(M)_s + (M)_t(1 - \theta) \quad \dots (12)$$

It may be mentioned again that the conditions to be satisfied for the application of the aforesaid equations are, that during titration the pH may change from its initial to a limiting value of about 5.8 and that the viscosity of the system should not change appreciably

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